

PROJECT

Agroecological Production of Jujube

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Historical Value and Identity

Jujube, also called 'Red date' or 'Chinese date', has origin in China, where it has been cultivated for more than 4,000 years. This crop was progressively spread by Romans throughout southern Europe. In Alentejo, Portugal, it is known among older people as *Jujubeira* or *Açufaifo*, and there are few remaining trees and tiny orchards, from the species *Ziziphus jujuba*. Jujubes can be consumed fresh or dry, but since its shelf-life is short, it is important to explore new processing technologies such as crystallized jujube, tea, juice, fermented juice (probiotic), jam, jelly, chutney, pickles and vinegar (Rashwan et. al, 2020).

Fresh Jujube (www.plantamus.pt/)

Nutritional Value

Jujube has high nutritional and biological value, revealing potential to be included in different food formulations to improve quality. Various parts of the plant have been used, not only as food but also as Chinese traditional medicine. The fruit (peel and pulp) is the main source of antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-obesity, anticancer, hepato-protective, antidiabetic, anti-microbial and cardioprotective effects (Rashwan et. al, 2020). When compared with the apple, the most similar fruit, it has more carbohydrates and more protein (see Table 1).

Orchards in Freixo do Meio

Freixo do Meio has several areas of orchards for production of fruits as citrus and olives. The two tiny orchards of jubuje tree at the farm, have different ages, origins (neighbours and tree nursery) and probably varieties. Both produce yearly an interesting amount of fruit requiring therefore non agricultural treatment at all.

Jujubeira (jujube tree) leaves sprouting - Freixo do Meio, Spring 2022

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Table 1. Comparison of the nutrition value between jujube and apple (Rashwan et. al, 2020; INSA, 2021).

Nutritional Value (100g)	Fresh Jujube	Fresh Apple	Dried Jujube	Dried Apple
Energy (kcal)	79	62	281	257
Carbohydrates (g)	20.23	13.1	72.52	57.1
Protein (g)	1.2	0.2	4.72	0.8
Fat (g)	0.2	0.5	0.5	0.3
Fiber (g)	—	2	6	9.5
Water (g)	77.86	83.4	20.19	29.6

Production in Freixo do Meio

Through the usual commercial channels, on the summer of 2021, **Freixo do Meio** started to sell small quantities of fresh Jujube fruits. The product was sold at 7 €/kg.

Jujubes on a tree, Freixo do Meio, Summer 2021

Red-Date or dried Jujube (<https://revistajardins.pt/>)

Motivation

In **Freixo do Meio**, trees are considered a key element in soil improvement, ecosystem regeneration, climate regulation and also food production. Jujube exists in small amounts in Alentejo, but has been shown to be rustic, well adapted and productive. Improvement on breeding, agroecological production or marketing of products would add value and promote its utilization.

RADIANT Project

In the context of the RADIANT project, **Freixo do Meio** recognises the opportunity to trial, improve and promote, the diversification of underutilized fruit tree crops in the farm.

Through the principles of agroecology and aiming an economical development for the jujube, we aim at the:

- Identification and selection of the most suitable varieties of jujube trees to be cultivated;
- Implementation of an Agroecological Orchard in the farm;
- Adaptation and improvement of the agroecological practices.

References

- Rashwan, A.K., Karim, N., Shishir, M.R., Bao, T., Lu, Y., & Chen, W.** (2020). Jujube fruit: A potential nutritious fruit for the development of functional food products. *Journal of Functional Foods*, 75, 104205.
- PortFIR, INSA Doutor Ricardo Jorge.** (2019). Tabela da Composição de Alimentos (versão 5.0 – 2021). Available at: <http://portfir.insa.pt>

